

Handy Functor Cheat Sheet

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1 Introduction

Exponential map $f^* : \Omega \times X \rightarrow \Omega_\Omega(X)$
 Recursion map $\overset{y}{x} : X^y - x^y \rightarrow X$
 Principal homomorphism $\rho_x : \phi - \rho_y(x)^y \rightarrow \rho_y$
 Bisimulation map $bisim_x : Bisim(x) \rightarrow \phi$
 Classifying map $\Phi_c^X : L_{a_i}^{a_j}(X) \rightarrow \phi - L_{a_i}^{a_j}$
 G^n -affine map $f^G : G - O_n \rightarrow O$
 G^n -isotropy $G_{x_{yz}} : G_{x_y} \rightarrow G_{\bar{x}} \times G_{x/y}^n$
 G^n -orbit $G_Q^n(X, Y) : X \rightarrow G^n$
 α -isomorphism type $I_\alpha : \bar{X} \rightarrow \Omega_{\mathcal{H}}(X)$
 $C\omega$ -set kinesis $C\omega_x^{x^y} : O_n^n \rightarrow C\omega_{x_y}$
 B -absorbing state $|B| \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_{a_i}^{\cong}$
 P -shadow $p : \delta \rightarrow |P|$
 s_u^a -action $\otimes_x^k : s_u^a \cong O_{3,1} \rightarrow \otimes_x^k$
 tot_{x_y} -implication $im_x : |tot| \rightarrow |tot_{x_y}|$
 S -embeddable $emb_S : S \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_S - S$
 $cvgy$ -incomplete $conv_{x_i} : \phi \rightarrow cvg_{x_i} \quad ag = bv \iff ag = bv : \bar{a} \quad (G \times A \times V)$
 $\bar{g} \stackrel{?}{=} \bar{b} \quad (G \times A \times V) \quad \bar{v}$
 $Q \vdash t \ \& : - \vdash_c Q$
 $xr \stackrel{k_0}{\sim} y \sim_{k_0}^k : xr^\infty \rightarrow xr^\infty$
 k_j -simple category $k_j \xrightarrow{\sim} \mathcal{H}_{kk}^\circ \cong \Omega^\infty \dots \overset{\circ}{\Omega}_{Nz}$
 xm -representation $\pi_\alpha : - \rightarrow (\pi, V)$
 $(\alpha - k)$ -map $h : \sigma_\alpha^M \rightarrow \Omega_{\Omega(\alpha-k)}(S)$
 $\Omega_{\mathcal{H}}$ -type $I_\alpha : \bar{X} \rightarrow \Omega_{\mathcal{H}}(X)$
 ∞_k -unit $U_n^\alpha : S^* \rightarrow O_1$
 A -(anti)-composition $A : \infty_n^{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_A^\circ$
 Trivial transitive group $t_z^{x_y} : xr_z^{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow \infty^{\Omega^v \Omega^v \dots |\Omega|}$
 $R(\Omega^{v^\infty})$ -representation
 (ϕ) -representation $R : \Omega^{\mathcal{H}} \rightarrow \Omega_v^v$
 $r\# : \phi \rightarrow \Omega_\Omega$

(α_κ, κ) -representation $rep_{\alpha_\kappa} : J_{\kappa_\kappa} \rightarrow \cong^{(\alpha_x, \kappa)}$ (κ_κ) -action $act_k : k_\kappa^{\infty k} \rightarrow k_\kappa^k$
 ϕ -maps $\phi : \kappa \rightarrow N_A$
 ϕ -maps $\phi : k \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_A$
pre-facade $\langle \omega_\omega \rangle \cong \inf_{(\infty^m)_{\omega_\omega} \cong cvg_{\mathcal{H}}^\infty}$
post-facade $\langle \mathcal{H}_{a_i}^\circ \rangle \cong \inf_{\omega_{a_i}^\infty \cong Cvg_{\mathcal{H}}^\omega}$
fictive operation $??(a \rightarrow (\phi^{\Omega a}))_i \rightarrow \Omega_\infty$
1-parameter $\langle \Omega/k_k^{\Omega k} \rangle / \Omega$
2-parameter $\langle \Omega/X^{\Omega Z} \rangle / \Omega$
3-parameter $\langle \Omega/X^{\Omega Z} \rangle / \Omega$
delta refinement $[\mathcal{H}^{\mathcal{H}_k}]$
 Q^n -refinement $[\Omega^n]$
description $[\{\cong\}]$
 (x, x^{-1}) -quasi-projection $Q_m^n : 1 - hom(T) \rightarrow D_{(x, x^{-1})}$
 $\tilde{p}$ -partition $[\Phi_E^\circ]$ cM -projection P_c
 Φ -projection $P(\sigma_s^s) : xm^s \rightarrow \Phi - \phi^{xm^s}$
 ϕ -distinguishability $dist_{x_y} : xy \rightarrow \phi$
 p -partition $p : \delta \rightarrow P$
 r -representation $r : R_\alpha^n \rightarrow \phi - R_\alpha^n$
 r -extension $\otimes_r : \mathcal{H}_{a_i}^{\otimes r} \cong \delta_r^{\infty r} \rightarrow \Omega_{\mathcal{H}_{a_i}^{\otimes r}}$
Approximation map $\Phi_\Omega : V \rightarrow b(V)$
Coalgebra map $\alpha_c : {}_X \text{Hom}(C, X) \rho \rightarrow \text{Hom}({}_X \text{Hom}(C, X), X)$
Coalgebra map $\alpha_x : Gr_{x_y} \rightarrow \text{Hom}(\Omega_{x_y}(x_y), x_y)$
 α -map $\alpha : S \times X \rightarrow S \times \Gamma X$
Double literal map $\leftrightarrow : \bar{\phi} \rightarrow \phi \rightarrow \bar{\phi}$ s -extension $\cong'_\infty : S^\infty \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_{-\infty}^\cong$
Leveling $\stackrel{\ll}{\leftarrow} \varepsilon : \phi^{x-x} \rightarrow \text{level}_{x-x}$
Partial lifting $\ell_x : (-) \downarrow_{x_y} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_{x_y}^x$
Right lifting $\downarrow_x : xr_x^{xr} \rightarrow \downarrow_{xr_x^{xr}}$
Lifting $\downarrow_x : \mathcal{H}_x^{xr} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}_{x_y}^{xr}$
 $\star$ -pullback $\stackrel{\star}{\leftarrow} : \Omega_{\mathcal{H}_{a_i}^{a_i}} AD \rightarrow \Omega_{\mathcal{H}_{a_i}^{a_i}} A$
 x -pushout $_x : xk_x \downarrow \rightarrow xk_x \downarrow_x^{\mathcal{H}}$
-pushout : $\rightarrow \infty_{\mathcal{H}}$
1-point extension $\tilde{q} : xm \rightarrow \tilde{q}\text{Hom}(X, \Sigma^{\mathbf{N}\mathbf{N}})$
 κ -reflection $1_{\kappa \leftrightarrow} : \kappa \rightarrow \kappa'$
Inclusion $k \Rightarrow k_j$
Extension $e : S \hookrightarrow Sc'$
 $p\mathcal{H}$ -reflection $k \rightarrow \phi - k$
Reflection $R : \tilde{I}_k^{\gamma_i} \rightarrow \phi - \tilde{I}_k^{\gamma_i}$
1-quasi-inclusion $T_a^b : x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}} \rightarrow x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}}$
0-quasi-inclusion $T_a^b : x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}} \rightarrow x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}}$
 $y = x$ -quasi-inclusion $T_a^b : x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}} \rightarrow x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}}$
 x_{-1} -quasi-inclusion $T_a^b : x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}} \rightarrow x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}}$
Set-theoretical embedding " $\in$ " : $T_a^b : x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}} \rightarrow x^{\infty^{\mathcal{H}}}$

$\tilde{g}_x$ -curve-arbitrary "R": $T_a^b : x^{\infty \mathcal{H}} \rightarrow x^{\infty \mathcal{H}}$
 Boen joint restriction $\wedge$: $T_a^b : x^{\infty \mathcal{H}} \rightarrow x^{\infty \mathcal{H}}$
 x -Gersten joint restriction $\wedge_{x_y}^x$: $T_a^b : x^{\infty \mathcal{H}} \rightarrow x^{\infty \mathcal{H}}$
 Joint surjection Φ, ϕ, μ $T_a^b : x^{\infty \mathcal{H}} \rightarrow x^{\infty \mathcal{H}}$
 Omega-bicompletion Φ, ϕ, μ, Ω
 Theorem $k \leftrightarrow \mathcal{H}$: $\tilde{g}_x \leftrightarrow h_{\mathcal{H}} = s^{s_s}$
 Deformation map $\gg$: $X_F \rightarrow \gg (X_F)$
 Connected homomorphism $\sigma^{X_\mu}(x_\mu) : X_\mu \rightarrow \sigma^{X_\mu}(X_\mu)$
 Diagonal embedding : $X \rightarrow X^{X \downarrow \Lambda^\infty}$
 Lift $\Lambda X : X \downarrow \Lambda^\infty \rightarrow X^\infty$
 Section $\text{sec } x : x_\Lambda \rightarrow \text{sec } X_\Lambda$
 $\downarrow$ -pullback $\downarrow : \mathcal{H}^\downarrow \langle \nu \rangle AB \rightarrow \mathcal{H}^\downarrow \langle \nu \rangle A \downarrow BB \downarrow A$
 Convolution integral $\mathcal{X}_\Lambda = \int_{\mathcal{H}_{a_i e m}^\Lambda} \mathcal{D}_{\alpha + \frac{1}{\infty}, f(\infty)} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (a_k \Omega_k^{\alpha + \frac{1}{\infty}} + \theta_k) \right) \tan^{-1}(x^{f(\infty)}; \zeta_x, m_x) dx$
 Normal fractional integral $11 + y^2 dx = \int_0^\infty 11 + y^2 dx$
 Inverse limit $\mathcal{O}_\infty := \mathcal{O}_n : \mathcal{O}_n \mathcal{O}_{n+1}$
 Inverse integral $\int dy y := \int_0^\infty dy y$
 The n-waveform is a mathematical representation of a wave through the equation

$$\psi_n(t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \cos(\omega_n t + \phi_n)$$

where A_n , ω_n , and ϕ_n are constants.

$$\mathcal{F}_{speck} = \sum_{i,j,k} \sin(\vec{p}_i \cdot \vec{q}_j) \cos(\vec{r}_k \cdot \vec{s}) - \sqrt{S_n T_m} \tan(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w}).$$

$$\varphi(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n) = \sqrt{\frac{\sin(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i) + \sum_m \cos\left(\prod_{j=1}^m y_j\right)}{\sqrt{\prod_{k=1}^n p_k}}}.$$

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{F}_{speck} \circ \mathcal{K}_{ker} \circ \text{Presheaf} \circ \mathcal{C}_{comp}$$

where $\mathcal{F}_{speck}$ is the Speck functor, $\mathcal{K}_{ker}$ is the Ker functor, Presheaf is the presheaf, and $\mathcal{C}_{comp}$ is the computational functor.

The global theory is then expressed as:

$$E_{total} = \Omega_\Lambda \left(\sin \theta \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{1}{n - l \tilde{x} \mathcal{R}} \right) \times \mathcal{H} \otimes \prod_{\Lambda} h - \cos \psi \diamond \theta \leftrightarrow \overset{ABC}{F} \right).$$

Speck functor:

$$\mathcal{F}_{speck} : (C, R, \Omega_\Lambda) \rightarrow (C', R', \Omega'_\Lambda)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{F}_{speck} = \sin(\vec{p}_i \cdot \vec{q}_j) \cos(\vec{r}_k \cdot \vec{s}) - \sqrt{S_n T_m} \tan(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w})$$

with

$$\Omega'_\Lambda \leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}_{speck}, \Omega_\Lambda, R, C \rightarrow R', C'.$$

Hom Functor:

$$\mathcal{H}_{geom} : (R, \Omega_\Lambda) \rightarrow (R', \Omega'_\Lambda)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{H}_{geom} = \sum_{i,j,k} \left(\sin(\vec{p}_i \cdot \vec{q}_j) \cos(\vec{r}_k \cdot \vec{s}) - \sqrt{S_n T_m} \tan(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w}) \right)$$

with

$$\Omega'_\Lambda \leftrightarrow \mathcal{H}_{geom}, \Omega_\Lambda, R \rightarrow R'.$$

Ker Functor:

$$\mathcal{K}_{simpl} : (R, \Omega_\Lambda) \rightarrow (R', \Omega'_\Lambda)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{K}_{simpl} = \sum_{i=1}^n \cos(\omega_i t + \phi_i)$$

with

$$\Omega'_\Lambda \leftrightarrow \mathcal{K}_{simpl}, \Omega_\Lambda, R \rightarrow R'.$$

Comp functor:

$$\mathcal{C}_{diff} : (R, \Omega_\Lambda) \rightarrow (R', \Omega'_\Lambda)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{C}_{diff} = \sqrt{\frac{\sin(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i) + \sum_m \cos(\prod_{j=1}^m y_j)}{\sqrt{\prod_{k=1}^n p_k}}}.$$

with

$$\Omega'_\Lambda \leftrightarrow \mathcal{C}_{diff}, \Omega_\Lambda, R \rightarrow R'.$$

Other Functors:

$$\mathcal{F}_{trans} : (C, R, \Omega_\Lambda) \rightarrow (C', R', \Omega'_\Lambda)$$

such that

$$\mathcal{F}_{trans} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\sin(\vec{a}_i \cdot \vec{b}_j) + \sum_m \cos(c_m)}{\sqrt{D_n E_m} \tan(\vec{d} \cdot \vec{e})}.$$

with

$$\Omega'_\Lambda \leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}_{trans}, \Omega_\Lambda, R, C \rightarrow R', C'.$$

Star Traveler Functor:

$$\mathcal{F}_{st} : (C, R) \rightarrow (C', R')$$

such that

$$\mathcal{F}_{st} = \sum_{i,j,k} \exp \left(\sqrt{\sum_n \sin(\vec{p}_i \cdot \vec{q}_j) \cos(\vec{r}_k \cdot \vec{s}) - \sqrt{S_n T_m} \tan(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w})} \right).$$

with

$$\Omega'_\Lambda \leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}_{st}, \Omega_\Lambda, R, C \rightarrow R', C'.$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{st}(F_{RNG}, \Omega_\Lambda, R, C) \rightarrow R'; C''$$

$\Rightarrow$

$$F'_{RNG} \cong F' : (\Omega'_\Lambda, R', C') \rightarrow (\Omega''_\Lambda, C'') \quad \text{such that} \quad \Omega_\Lambda \leftrightarrow (F', \Omega'_\Lambda, R', C') \rightarrow C''.$$

2 References

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